

Fundamental Studies on the Interaction of Carbohydrate Derivatives with Alkaline Earth Metals.

*II. Reaction of Ethanolamine, Ethylenediamine and 2-Aminoglucose with the Halides of Alkaline Earth Metals†

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Adducts of ethanolamine, ethylenediamine, 2-aminoglucose with Ca^{++} , Ba^{++} and Sr^{++} have been reported. The molar compositions of these adducts are the following: Ca^{++} -ethanolamine is 1 : 2, Ca^{++} -ethylenediamine is 1 : 4, Sr^{++} -ethylenediamine is 1 : 4 and Ca^{++} , Ba^{++} and Sr^{++} adducts of 2-aminoglucose are all 1 : 2. Almost all of these adducts are hygroscopic and only stable in anhydrous condition. They also decompose at elevated temperature. They are highly soluble in water but practically insoluble in most of the nonaqueous solvents.

Evidences of only limited number of metal complexes of carbohydrates and their derivatives are given in literature¹⁻⁵. Our interest is mainly on alkaline earth metal adducts of carbohydrate and their suitable derivatives. 2-aminoglucose has been used in this study and amino compounds like ethanolamine and ethylenediamine have been used with a view to understand the role of NH_2 group in linking the weak complexing alkaline earth metal ions. Mg^{++} and transition metal ions have been known⁶ to form complexes with amines. Some calcium complexes of *o*-phosphorylated peptides are also known^{7,8}. However, report of alkaline earth metal adducts of free amines are but very scarce.

EXPERIMENTAL

The alkaline earth metal chlorides used were all E. Merck pro-analyse grade. Ethanolamine of B.D.H., pure (99%) and ethylenediamine of Riedel (98%) were further purified by distillation in presence of NaOH. 2-aminoglucose hydrochloride was prepared in this laboratory by the hydrolysis of chitin occurring in Lobsters' shells. The purity of the recrystallised product was checked by paper chromatography.

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Preparation of the adducts: Saturated solutions of CaCl_2 , $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and ethanolamine in methanol were mixed at room temperature keeping the amine a little excess. The solution became hot. This was kept in the refrigerator overnight. After siphoning off the supernatant liquid the residue was shaken with small portions of CHCl_3 decanting off the solvent as far as practicable each time. After 10–12 such treatments the mass was filtered under suction employing CHCl_3 for further working. The CHCl_3 treatment was made to eliminate excess unreacted amine. Finally the adduct was dried under vacuum in a desiccator for 12 hr and stored in the desiccator.

Exactly same procedure was followed for preparing the ethylenediamine adduct of CaCl_2 . However, in this case purification was made by recrystallising the adduct from methanol solution. It has been observed that this adduct is stable at low temperature.

The adduct of SrCl_2 -ethylenediamine was prepared by reacting the components directly in presence of a small amount of alcohol. The mixture was given 48 hrs to react. Finally, purification was made adopting the CHCl_3 washing technique as mentioned above.

2-aminoglucose adducts of CaCl_2 , BaCl_2 and SrCl_2 were prepared in the following manner. 2-aminoglucose hydrochloride solution in rectified spirit was treated with Dowex 40 anion exchange resin. The solution of the free aminoglucose was concentrated under vacuum and made into three equal parts. In these, calculated amounts (Salt : Carbohydrate as 1 : 2) of the salts CaCl_2 , BaCl_2 and SrCl_2 were added. The solutions were stirred well to dissolve the salts. The solutions were then kept in a refrigerator for a week and afterwards observed to have a small amount of crystals appeared on the bottom of each flask. They were then filtered and further concentrated up to the point of crystal appearance. After storing in the refrigerator for overnight the crystals were separated by filtration under vacuum, washing with small portions of Dioxane-Water mixture (2 : 1) for 10–12 times. The crystals were then dried under vacuum in a desiccator and stored in there. The mother liquor of each of these reactions was found to give more precipitate on storing. Assuming some unreacted salt might have been appeared by the action of Dioxane in the solution these were discarded.

In the course of the experiment it was observed that the solutions which contained CaCl_2 and SrCl_2 became a little yellow in colour. The one containing BaCl_2 was colourless. The colouration may be due to the decomposition of the unreacted amino sugar and to our observations the extent of decomposition is more in the presence of CaCl_2 compared to that in the presence of SrCl_2 .

Paper Chromatography: Whatman No. 3 paper was used for the chromatography. Pure violuric acid (in water) and ninhydrin (in *n*-butanol and acetic acid) were used as spraying reagents. The solvents used were *n*-Butanol-dry Ethanol-Pyridine in the ratio 4 : 1 : 0.1 for Ca-ethanolamine adduct, and ethylacetate—pyridine—water in the ratio 8 : 2 : 1 for Ca-ethylenediamine and Sr-ethylenediamine adducts.

Analyses : Both volumetric and gravimetric methods⁹ were utilised for the estimation of the metals and chloride. The elements C, H and N were estimated microanalytically.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chromatographic methods were used to check the formation of new compounds. It should be noted in the beginning that the compounds are very unstable and therefore choice of proper conditions for chromatography appears to be a great problem. After many trial experiments it was seen that the solvent system ethylacetate—pyridine—water in the ratio 8 : 2 : 1 can be used for the identification of ethylenediamine adducts of Ca^{++} and Sr^{++} . Ninhydrin spraying after the run developed well defined individual spots. Spraying by violuric acid did not give separate spots indicating movement of the metallic part together with the amine part of the adduct, thus suggesting non-separation of the components. In the case of Ca-ethanolamine adduct chromatographic identification was extremely difficult. However, a solvent system of *n*-Butanol—Dry ethanol—Pyridine in the ratio 4 : 1 : 0.1 was used and definite new spots for the adduct samples were obtained. In this case part of the calcium and the amine were observed to get separated from the main adducts. Spraying by violuric acid and ninhydrin was used. The chromatographic results are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. It should be mentioned that in all the cases adducts moved slower than the pure amine. The R_f value of the adducts with reference to the amines are the following :

Ca-ethanolamine	...	0.18
Ca-ethylenediamine	...	0.86
Sr-ethylenediamine	...	0.90

It should be mentioned in this connection that the chromatographic spots for the adducts are more or less like elongated bands. We presume that this is a property of the ligands

Fig. 1. Paper chromatography of calcium ethanolamine.
 1, 5 : Ethanolamine; 2, 4 : Ca-Ethanolamine; 3 : CaCl_2 ; A : Spot for the adduct (unbroken)
 Shaded area : Violuric acid spray; Hatched area : Ninhydrin spray.

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used. They also develop elongated bands after spraying with the reagent ninhydrin. The adducts of 2-aminoglucose could not be identified by chromatography. Probably they break completely in solution.

Fig 2 Paper chromatography of Ethylenediamine adducts of calcium and strontium
1 and 4: Ethylenediamine; 2: Sr-Ethylenediamine; 3: Ca-Ethylenediamine
Shaded area: V₂O₅ spray, Open area: Ninhydrin spray

The results of the elemental analyses correspond to the compositions of the adducts as given in Table I. The agreement between calculated and obtained percentage compositions is not very good in several cases. This can certainly happen as the adducts prepared are not very pure. Purification by recrystallization is a serious problem, because the compounds are very hygroscopic and unstable in solution. Only Ca-ethanolamine could be recrystallized from dry methanol solution.

TABLE 1

Analytical data of the compounds

Compounds	% Yield	% Metal		%Cl		%C		%N		%H	
		Calc	Obs	Calc	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.
CaCl ₂ -Ethanolamine (1 : 2) white	37	17.6	18.1	30.7	29.8	20.8	19.1	12.1	10.7	6.1	6.1
CaCl ₂ -Ethylenediamine (1 : 4) light yellow	40	11.4	11.0	20.2	20.4	27.4	26.2	31.9	27.1	9.1	9.5
CaCl ₂ -Aminoglucose (1 : 2) colourless*	12	8.5	8.4	17.4	15.2	30.6	32.4	—	—	6.0	6.6
BaCl ₂ -Aminoglucose (1 : 2) white	25	26.0	26.2	12.5	14.6	25.9	26.0	5.0	5.5	—	—
SrCl ₂ -Aminoglucose (1 : 2) white	20	17.0	20.0	13.8	15.8	—	—	—	—	—	—
SrCl ₂ -Ethylenediamine (1 : 4) light yellow	40	22.0	22.7	17.9	18.8	24.4	20.0	—	—	8.0	7.5

* The colour changes to brownish on standing.

As regards the proneness to hygroscopicity the Ca-ethanolamine, Ca-ethylenediamine and Sr-ethylenediamine are very hygroscopic. Ca-2-aminoglucose is also hygroscopic but the corresponding Ba- and Sr-compounds are more stable toward moisture. The hygroscopicity of the above three compounds follow the order exhibited by the corresponding chlorides of Ca^{+2} , Ba^{+2} and Sr^{+2} . All these compounds do not have sharp melting points, they decompose instead (2-aminoglucose adducts swell prior to decomposition).

It can be mentioned in this connection that ethanolamine only forms compound with calcium chloride, barium and strontium chloride do not give any compound in the solid state. Whereas both calcium and strontium produce adducts with ethylenediamine. This exhibits affinity of the donor and acceptor parts toward one another. Among the alkaline earth metals calcium complexes are more abandoned and stable than those of strontium and barium. This tendency is exhibited in the investigation reported herewith. However, 2-aminoglucose has become an exception and given adducts with all the alkaline earth metal chlorides.

Solubility of the compounds were checked with various nonaqueous solvents (DMSO, DMF, CCl_4 , THF, Dioxane, Acetone, Ethylacetate, Ethanol (abs.), ethyleneglycolmonomethylether). It was observed that the compounds have poor solubility in most of the solvents. They are completely soluble in water and decomposes gradually. We conclude that under the experimental conditions described so far definite amine and glucosamine adducts of alkaline earth metal chlorides could be prepared.

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